

THE STRENGTH OF SINGLE FIBRES AND SIMPLE ARRAYS OF FIBRES IN A MODEL COMPOSITE SYSTEM

Part 2 : Statistical aspects of failure

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ABSTRACT

The composites consisted of arrays of 10 parallel silicon carbide fibres set in an epoxy resin matrix. The fibres were 100 μm diameter and had been formed by depositing SiC onto a 20 μm diameter tungsten core. The fibre spacing (centre to centre) was varied between 2 and 10 fibre diameters. The test coupon was extended monotonically in tension and the strain and position of each fibre fracture was recorded throughout the test as described in Part 1 of this paper.

The objective of this analysis is to relate the strength of the composite to that of the fibre and to determine the extent to which a failure in one fibre will influence failure in an adjacent fibre and the overall pattern of failure of the composite. This calls for a complex statistical model, but under certain assumptions it is possible to calculate the probabilities of observed patterns of failed and unfailed fibres, as a function of unknown stress concentration parameters. The method of maximum likelihood can then be applied to make inferences about those parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Many of the theoretical models for fibrous composites are concerned with fibres arranged in a linear equally-spaced array. The "chain-of-bundles" model [1,2] treats a set of N parallel fibres as a set of m independent sub-bundles of length d . The choice of d is, to some extent arbitrary, but is taken to realistically represent twice the ineffective length i.e. the length of fibre surrounding a break over which load transfer will take place. It is therefore expected that no more than one break may appear in any fibre element of length d . The load on an unfailed fibre in a sub-bundle will depend on how many failed fibres are adjacent to it. The notion that the sub-bundles are completely independent is, in practice, an approximation, but Wolstenholme & Smith [3] applied the model to a glass-carbon hybrid [4] and showed that the method has considerable potential. The composite considered here, however, poses additional problems. In particular, the idea of independent sub-bundles is clearly not appropriate as the 'damage zone' resulting from each fibre break affects a wide and greatly varying length of the material (Fig 1). It appears that the fibres become decoupled from the matrix either side of a break due to a shock-induced debonding at the fibre/matrix interface. It is no longer possible to look at a length d of the array in isolation. Therefore a method has been devised whereby the

entire array can be considered at any point in the failure process.

THE STATISTICAL MODEL

Each of the N fibres of length L is treated as m elements of length d , and a likelihood function is formed for the complete array by considering what has happened to each of the $N \times m$ elements. An element may have

- i) failed at a certain stress
- ii) become decoupled from the matrix due to failure of a near neighbour.
- iii) survived the maximum applied stress

In assessing the effective stress at which failure or survival took place, account is taken of the adjacent elements in neighbouring fibres. Where there is decoupling or failure, load is deemed to be passed to corresponding elements in the nearest surviving neighbours. The enhancement of effective load may be reflected in the application of a stress concentration factor k . When the applied stress is x the fibre experiences stress kx . As failures and damaged elements accumulate around a fibre so this factor k will increase from its initial value of one as indicated in Fig 1.

Suppose that the stress distribution for a fibre length d is $F(x)$ and correspondingly the probability density $f(x)$. Then the probability that an element fails at stress x when its stress concentration factor is k is the differential $dF(kx)/dx = kf(kx)dx$ the probability that the element survives stress x is $1-F(kx)$, and if failure can only be determined as having occurred when the stress concentration factor was somewhere between k and k' , ($k' > k$) then the probability is $F(k'x) - F(kx)$.

A certain difficulty arises with regard to the recording of failures apparently occurring simultaneously. Where two failures do not coincide in that their damage zones do not overlap or they occur in the same fibre then they can be regarded as independent events. But where a connection is possible, all possible orders of failure, where some failures triggered others, must be taken into account. This leads to considerable calculation even for three 'simultaneous' failures, and requires numerical integration or some approximation in order to estimate survival probabilities.

Once a probability $p(i,j)$ can be assigned to each element (i,j) then the likelihood function is given by

$$L(\theta) = \prod_j p(i,j)$$

and can be maximised with respect to any unknown parameters θ .

ASSUMPTIONS

The load concentration factor k is of the general form $1 + g(r)$ where r is the number of adjacent failed fibres. Following Bader & Pitkethly, and Wolstenholme & Smith, $g(r)$ is assumed to be \sqrt{r}/F , where F is termed the load sharing parameter and it is the estimation of F which is the principal objective here. It is to be expected that F will increase with inter-fibre separation, and that beyond a spacing

of approximately five fibre diameters F will effectively be infinity, the excess load at such distances being absorbed by the matrix.

The model (Fig 1) defines a constant load redistribution along the entire length of a damaged region. It is a simple matter to weight the distribution at certain points, e.g. at failed points or extremes of damaged zones. Another feature of certain of the samples studied is the appearance of resin cracks between fibres at higher stresses. These too can be accommodated in terms of their effect on load concentration factors provided that the effect can be reasonably defined. The situation arises with these SiC fibres where an element may have a large number of failed or damaged neighbours stretching across quite large distances. It seems reasonable to suggest that only those neighbours within a certain distance will affect the load concentration factor. So accordingly an upper limit was placed on the value of r_1 and r_2 where $r = r_1 + r_2$, and r_1 and r_2 being the number of failed/damaged neighbours on the two sides of each element.

The choice of d is again somewhat arbitrary, but here is not of any particular physical significance. The value chosen should be designed to combine numerical accuracy with acceptable computation time, and most importantly be such that the function $f(x)$ may be defined reliably.

The positions of fibre breaks and damage zones were recorded to 0.5 mm accuracy. Typical failure patterns are shown in Fig 2. A value of 1mm was chosen for d , small enough to make each element fall clearly into one of the three categories above, but large enough to keep the number of terms contributing to the likelihood function computationally acceptable (in this case 2000). This then requires that the strength distribution of fibres of length 1 mm be defined.

Tests on single fibres in resin revealed that lengths in the range 50 to 200 mm conformed well to a Weibull distribution, and yielded similar estimates of the parameters. It was implied that the fibres would therefore "weak-link" scale and a distribution of strength for 1mm fibres deduced. The Weibull distribution gives for length L

$$1 - F_L(x) = \exp(-L(x/\alpha)^w)$$

and weak-link scaling assumes

$$1 - F_L(x) = (1 - F_1(x))^L$$

implying that

$$F_1(x) = \exp(-(x/\alpha)^w)$$

It was clear, however, that arrays of 10 fibres behaved rather differently, dependent on the fibre-to-fibre separation.

STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION

Every fibre in each array was examined to find the strain at which the first failure occurred. Where this may have been influenced by a previously occurring failure in a neighbouring fibre, the strain was recorded as a censored observation i.e. all we can say is that the fibre survived to at least this strain. For each fibre spacing the

parameters w and α were estimated by maximum likelihood, where w is the Weibull exponent and α the characteristic stress of fibres length $d(1\text{mm})$.

TABLE 1 INITIAL FAILURE ANALYSIS

Fibre separation (diameters)	No. Uncensored Observations	No. Censored Observations	Estimated w	Estimated α (GPa)	Equivalent % strain (200 mm.)
10	17	3	16.7	4.875	1.023
8	28	12	14.8	4.885	0.984
6	45	5	7.9	5.572	0.821
4	69	11	6.1	6.848	0.828
2	28	12	8.6	5.376	0.837

A 95% confidence region for w and α may be formed for all pairs of values for which twice the log-likelihood function is within 5.99 of its maximum. This is derived from the Chi-squared approximation, which is a standard method for forming approximate confidence regions from the likelihood function. The smaller the region, the more precise the estimation, and this is essentially a function of the number of uncensored observations. It is apparent that the 8 and 10 diameter arrays conform well to the single fibre results which gave $w = 13.9$ and $\alpha = 4.98$. There is however a clear effect at closer spacings (Fig 3). Probability plots, suitably adjusted using Kaplan-Meier estimation [5] of the survivor function, in order to take account of the censoring, tend to indicate proximity to a Weibull distribution even at the closer spacings. Assuming therefore that the strength of unit length fibres could be estimated, this was taken for each spacing to be the distribution indicated by the initial failures.

ESTIMATION OF F

Having defined the unit length distribution completely the likelihood function for each spacing became purely a function of the unknown F . The complexity of the function requires the maximum to be found numerically. The results were as follows:

TABLE 2 ESTIMATION OF F

Fibre separation	F	95% conf.interval
2 diameter	11	[9, 15]
4 diameter	24	[18, 37]
6 diameter	86	[51, 174]
8 diameter	201	[53,]
10 diameter	420	[93,]

The wide and unbounded confidence intervals at the large spacings is a clear indication that negligible load-sharing is likely, and at closer spacings F behaves exactly as would be expected.

FURTHER DISCUSSION

Additional data was available for some of the data sets, beyond the point where some cracks in the matrix started to appear. An attempt might be made to model the effect by adjusting load concentration factors in the region of a crack, and then to re-estimate F in the light of this additional information. However it is quite likely that at the higher stresses at which the resin cracks appear, there is also a change in the behaviour of fibre strength. As demonstrated in Part 1 there are two distinct modes of failure for these fibres, surface and core-initiated, and whilst embedding these fibres in resin matrix inhibits the surface flaws, the indications are that for the closer array spacings at least, the different failure modes must be incorporated for the information at higher stress levels to yield more precise results.

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Fig.1 Schematic representation of interactions between broken and decoupled fibre segments and their unbroken neighbours. The segments marked 1, 2 and 3 have 1, 2 and 3 broken or decoupled segments respectively. The appropriate calculations for their stress concentration k is indicated.

Fig.2 Three diagrams of failure patterns taken from typical experimental results. At the 10 diameter spacing there is no obvious interaction but at 2 diameter a very strong interaction is apparent.

Fig 3. The relationship between the Weibull exponent, w , and the characteristic strength at unit length, α . The closed loops enclose all the data points at each indicated separation. There is a clear distinction between the two widest spacings. (See also Table 2 in Part 1 of this paper.)